

Implications of Finite Element Analysis in Orthodontics.

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Abstract-

Background- Orthodontics, a branch of dentistry focused on realigning teeth, has benefited from the application of Finite Element Analysis (FEA). FEA is a computational method that calculates stress and displacement within structures under specific loads. In orthodontics, FEA has been used to analyze the biomechanical effects of treatment methods and understand bone remodeling. This article provides an overview of FEA in orthodontics, discussing its fundamentals and outlining the steps involved in the process. FEA allows for accurate quantification of stress and strain patterns in the periodontal ligament, bone, and tooth structures, contributing to improved understanding and precision in orthodontic treatment. Computed Tomography (CT) scans are used to generate FEA models, and morphological analysis provides insights into the characteristics of dental structures. FEA is also used to study bone remodeling and dentofacial orthopaedics. However, FEA has limitations, including the need for careful modeling and the cost involved. Overall, FEA has proven to be a valuable tool in orthodontics, enhancing treatment planning and providing insights into the biomechanics of tooth movement and bone remodeling. Conclusion- Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is a powerful tool in orthodontics that allows for the accurate quantification of stress and strain patterns in the teeth, periodontal ligament, and bone structures during orthodontic tooth movement. It provides valuable insights into the structural behavior of teeth and helps improve treatment planning and outcomes. While FEA has its limitations and should be complemented by clinical trials, its application in orthodontics holds great promise for advancing evidence-based practices and customized treatment approaches.

Keywords- Finite Element Analysis, Geometric model construction, Dentofacial orthopaedics.

Introduction-

Orthodontics is a branch of dentistry that uses force delivery systems to realign teeth. It has connections to engineering and physics principles, as forces and their consequences play a crucial role in orthodontic treatment. The objectives of orthodontics include improving function, aesthetics, and oral hygiene.⁽¹⁾ Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is a computational method initially proposed in 1956 that has been widely used in various fields, including engineering. FEA calculates stress and displacement within a structure under specific loads. In orthodontics, FEA has been employed as a powerful tool to analyze the biomechanical effects of different treatment methods and understand the complex bone response to external stresses. By assessing stress, strain, and displacement in living tissues, FEA helps comprehend bone remodeling and in regards to the treatment outcomes.⁽²⁾ The article discusses the fundamentals of FEA and how it is used in orthodontics, outlining each stage of the process.

Utility of Fem-

Orthodontics is shifting towards evidence-based practices backed by scientific research.⁽³⁾ Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is a valuable tool used in orthodontics to study the structural behavior of teeth, considering factors such as material characteristics and geometry.⁽⁴⁾ FEA allows for accurate quantification of stress and strain patterns in the periodontal ligament, bone, and tooth structures during orthodontic tooth movement. Additionally, it can simulate the stresses acting on a single tooth, account for variations in root length, and describe how the periodontal ligament varies with age.⁽⁵⁾ These advancements in research and FEA contribute to the improved understanding and precision of orthodontic treatment.

Road to FEM-

The Finite Element Method (FEM) involves dividing a complex structure into smaller components or elements based on physical characteristics. This approach, known as finite element analysis, allows for the study of how the structure responds to external stimuli, including orthodontic forces. The FEM utilizes nodal points as building blocks, forming a meshwork that simplifies the structure.⁽⁶⁾ This method offers control over the level of simplification, providing advantages over other approaches.⁽⁷⁾ Pre-surgical planning may be done using FEM, and it has the potential to take the role of stereolithographic models. Each element in FEM is defined by an assumed shape function that expresses internal displacement as a function of nodal displacement. This means that an element may provide an accurate response for a specific support and loading scenario but could yield an incorrect response for different conditions.⁽⁸⁾

Steps in FEM-

1. The geometric model construction.
2. The geometric model to a Finite element analysis model conversion.
3. Data representation of the material properties.
4. The boundary condition defining.
5. Application of the load.
6. Solution to the linear algebraic equation system.
7. Analyzing the results.⁽⁸⁾

Basic Steps in Finite Element Method:-

The Geometric Model Construction-

To analyze a geometrical model, it can be created in a CAD program and imported into analysis software, or computed tomography images can be used as a geometrical model. The model must meet specific conditions and be saved with the appropriate file extensions.

Discretization Process-

Discretization is a method that breaks down the domain or component into smaller elements connected by nodes. By examining the stress distribution inside each piece and integrating them to create an overall stress distribution, this approach increases accuracy. This process allows for a precise visualization of the component's stress distribution.

Applying Material Properties-

In this stage, the mechanical properties of the component, such as Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, are determined and assigned to the model. These properties are essential for calculating the response of the component to stress. The operator specifies the type of element to be used and assigns the appropriate properties.

Defining Boundary Conditions & Nature of Problem-

The boundary condition is chosen depending upon the mode of analysis such as structural, dynamic, thermal, fluid etc.

Application of Load-

Boundary constraints are applied to the discretized domain, and known loads are applied to the nodes based on the geometry of the component. Different types of loads, such as pressure, gravity, forces, or moments, are used depending on the analysis requirements, such as structural or thermal issues.

Results-

The results can be obtained quickly and accurately through model images representing different stress levels using color-coded representations. A color chart is provided for interpretation. The results can be compiled and sent for further analysis.

Computed Tomography (CT) & Extraction of Morphological Parameters From CT Scans -

Computed tomography (CT) is an imaging technique that creates cross-sectional images of objects by capturing transmission or reflection data from multiple angles. It involves exposing a sample to radiation and measuring the amount of radiation transmitted or reflected. The resulting projections represent the attenuation of X-rays or other radiation within the object. These projections can be reconstructed to create 2D maps of the attenuation coefficient distribution, which can be stacked to form a 3D image. Hounsfield Units (HU) are used to quantify attenuation coefficients. CT is used to create a 3D model of bone microstructure, which can be further analyzed using morphological examination.⁽⁹⁾ fig 1

Fig. 1- Conversion of CT scan into Finite element model.

Generation of FEM Model-

The geometry of the tooth and periodontal tissues, the properties of the materials, and the distribution of loads are the major aspects to take into account while building a three-dimensional finite element tooth model. Nodes represent points at the corners of elements that define the tooth and periodontium structure, and boundary conditions are assigned to these nodes. Each component is assigned specific material properties. Creating a 3D model requires accurate geometric input, typically obtained through CT scans. The model is meshed, and material attributes are assigned to each component.⁽⁹⁾ fig. 2

Fig. 2 FEM model of skull

Morphological Analysis-

Morphological analysis involves extracting morphological parameters from an object. The parameters include tissue volume (TV), bone volume (BV), trabecular thickness (Tb.Th), and the ratio of BV to TV. TV quantifies the volume of the overall region of interest, while BV represents the volume of the solid phase. Tb.Th refers to the thickness of the trabecular rods, and BV/TV is the ratio of bone volume to tissue volume. These parameters provide insights into the morphological characteristics of the object.⁽¹⁰⁾

Distribution of Trabecular Thickness-

Trabecular thickness (Tb.Th) is determined by finding the largest sphere that fits within a point inside the body, considering the distribution and thickness of trabeculae. This calculation involves constructing the object's body and considering the trabecular midline.^(11,12)

Fundamentals in non linear computation method - Biomechanics, a field rooted in mechanics, focuses on the application of forces and how living organisms respond to them. It is important to understand mechanics in order to grasp the principles of biomechanics. This interdisciplinary field encompasses various levels of organization, from subatomic particles to the organized structures of living bodies, and utilizes different branches of mechanics to study phenomena at different scales.⁽¹³⁾

Finite strains associated with a body in its kinetics - Continuum mechanics theory states that the volume of a body at a given time is denoted as $V(t)$, and the surface area is represented by $S(t)$. A change in dimension occurs when the body is put under stress. It is crucial to have a solid understanding of kinematics to comprehend the transition in shape of the body before and after applying stress.⁽¹⁴⁾

Biomechanics of Bone Remodelling in Orthodontics Models-

Mathematical models, including analytical and numerical finite element models, play a significant role in dentistry for research and treatment planning. These models focus on tooth movement and the constitutive models applied to dental tissues. However, implant-related issues are not considered in the current discussion. The models primarily examine the forces applied, while the mechanisms of force delivery, such as brackets, are not taken into account.⁽¹⁵⁾

Gingiva- The gingival tissue surrounding the dental arch acts as additional support for the teeth and tends to contract, causing asymmetrical behavior during tooth rotation. The presence of collagen in the gingiva gives it a viscous quality. However, the mechanical activity of the gingiva is often overlooked in finite element investigations of tooth movement.⁽¹⁶⁾

Dental components- Enamel is a hard and brittle substance composed mainly of inorganic components. Cementum has limited research but has been studied for its physical properties. Dentin is strengthened by tubules and exhibits viscoelastic properties. Dental pulp is poorly characterized. The periodontal ligament (PDL) is a connective tissue that secures teeth to the bone, showcases as a shock absorber, and transfers forces during chewing. The PDL is considered bilinear elastic or non-linear, depending on the study. Various models, including elastic, viscoelastic, and poroelastic, have been used to simulate PDL behavior.^(17,18) fig 3

Fig. 3 Mesh Model after assigning material properties for Dento-Alveolar complex.

Orthodontic Tooth Movement Model-

A. Initial tooth movement- The finite element method (FEM) has been utilized in orthopaedic biomechanics and orthodontics since the 1970s. It is commonly used to analyze stress patterns, improve appliance design, and study material properties and bone responses in dentistry. Biomechanics is integrated into orthodontics, with a focus on the non-linear behavior of the periodontal ligament. Early orthodontic models examined tooth movements following the application of forces, while recent research incorporates more complex force systems and geometrical constraints. Models consider factors like non-uniform bone density, anisotropic nature of the periodontal ligament, and orthotropic behavior of the bone.^(19,20)

B. Long term tooth movement- The pressure tension hypothesis states that initial tooth movement is driven by the periodontal ligament (PDL) fibers. The tooth then becomes robust in its new location. Finite element analysis (FEA) models may incorporate bone remodeling laws to update displacement or forces based on stimuli like strain energy density or stress energy density. These models follow equilibrium principles to analyze forces and tooth movement from start to finish.⁽²¹⁾

Dentofacial Orthopaedics Modelling-

Finite element models of the mandible and maxilla have been used in orthodontics since the 1980s. These models represent the structure of bone and its properties using analogous components. Factors such as the magnitude of forces applied by orthodontic equipment and the temporomandibular joint (TMJ) movement are considered in the model. The materials used to simulate bones are typically linear elastic, distinguishing cortical bone from trabecular bone. The depiction of teeth varies among craniofacial models. TMJ models may incorporate linear elastic or hyperelastic materials to depict cartilage and discs. Muscle activation can be incorporated through inverse dynamic analysis or by modeling specific muscles using spring models. These models can also predict how the face bones and skull would react when confronted with external orthopaedic devices.⁽²²⁾

Bone Remodelling Models-

Bone remodeling is a self-organized process involving the actions of osteoblasts and osteoclasts, which contribute to bone stability and growth. An orthodontist must have a brief knowledge of bone remodeling process to predict tooth movement. The “Roux hypothesis:” states that bone becomes stiff, stress is generated, and the bone structure complies with “Wolff’s law” in response to applied forces. The “Frost model”, known as the mechanostat theory, explains that bone formation occurs when stress exceeds a certain threshold, while bone loss can occur if stress is below the optimal level. Both models work together to maintain equilibrium. Mathematical equations are used to computationally model bone behavior, considering factors like poroelasticity and remodeling depth.⁽²³⁾

FEM in Orthodontic Tooth Movement –

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is a theoretical study concept that should be complemented by clinical trials in orthodontics. FEA considers material properties, geometry, and initial forces to predict the final tooth position accurately. It plays a crucial role in understanding the stress-strain relationships across the tooth, periodontal ligament (PDL), and alveolar bone. The PDL’s viscous nature and energy storage contribute to bone remodeling. Different types of forces, such as longitudinal, compressive, and shear, can act on teeth in various orientations. The stress distribution along the crest of the alveolar bone varies depending on the forces applied, with the highest stress occurring near the apex and cervical level. The accuracy of FEA results depends on the model, material properties, and boundary conditions used. Friction in orthodontic systems can significantly affect the tension created in the PDL. Clinical trials and further considerations are necessary to fully understand and utilize the implications of FEA in orthodontics.⁽²⁴⁾

Limitations of FEM -

The use of theoretical models in biological systems, such as Finite Element Analysis (FEA), comes with limitations that must be considered. Inaccurate outcomes may occur from modelling errors, especially those involving material characteristics and boundary conditions. The complexity and dependence on computer programs require careful consideration during the modeling phase. Replicating live biological material in mechanical models is challenging.⁽²⁵⁾ Additionally, the cost of FEA research is a major limitation, making it impractical to use for every patient in dentistry or orthodontics.

Conclusion-

The movement of teeth within the jaw bones, a challenging and drawn-out procedure, is the major focus of orthodontics. Predicting the final tooth position accurately can save time and minimize patient discomfort. The link between the mechanical and biological reactions of the alveolar bone and periodontal ligament (PDL) to orthodontic forces can be better understood with the use of biomechanical models like the Finite Element Method (FEM). FEM is a precise engineering method with prospective uses in biomedical research, dentistry, and orthodontics. However, it is important to recognize that each individual is unique, and no single FEM study can accurately predict outcomes for all patients. Customized FEM research based on individual characteristics is necessary for more accurate predictions.

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